

Implementation of the Epi Training Kit: Impact Report

Epi Training Kit: An open-access online training strategy
in infectious disease modeling and public health data
science

EpiVerse TRACE-LAC
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Epi Training Kit Overview

What is the Epi Training Kit (EpiTKit)?

The Epi Training Kit (EpiTKit) is a training strategy in mathematical modelling of infectious diseases and public health data science, developed by the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana. Its main objective is to provide open-access educational material in Spanish, tailored to the context of Latin America and the Caribbean, to strengthen capacities in data science and mathematical modelling of infectious diseases in the region. Additionally, it promotes gender equity in these fields to ensure a more inclusive and effective development in response to public health emergencies.

The Epi Training Kit (EpiTKit) is part of an international collaboration that includes institutions such as the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana and the Universidad de los Andes in Colombia, the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine in the United Kingdom, the Medical Research Council Unit in Gambia, and data.org. This strategy is financially supported by the International Development Research Centre (IDRC) of Canada.

Motivation

Data science and mathematical modelling have become key tools to support the management and response to public health emergencies. However, in Latin America and the Caribbean, the availability of educational materials in Spanish remains limited, intensified by social, economic, and access barriers to quality open education. Additionally, there is a significant gap in the participation and representation of women in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) disciplines, especially in mathematical modelling, programming, and data science, which restricts the potential for advances in regional public health. In this context, the Epi Training Kit (EpiTKit) emerges as an innovative e-learning strategy designed to overcome these barriers by offering high-quality open-access education through a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course). Furthermore, it promotes gender equity in these fields, ensuring a more inclusive and effective development in response to public health emergencies in the region.

Target Audience

The Epi Training Kit is aimed at professionals and students in fields such as the health sector and STEM areas (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics), as well as individuals involved in public health decision-making.

Content & Delivery

The Epi Training Kit (EpiTKit) offered a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) on the edX Edge platform from Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, running from October 15 to December 20. The course includes concise learning units organized into four main modules: Epidemic and Epidemiological Theory, Data Science in Public Health, Outbreak Response and Modeling, and Advanced Analytics. Each module is structured into individual units, with each unit averaging 3 to 5 hours of study time, depending on the learner's pace and prior knowledge. This course is fully asynchronous and flexible, allowing students to progress at their own pace

The Epi Training Kit presently includes 10 learning units:

- History of Epidemics and Pandemics
- Introduction to Epidemic Theory
- General Epidemiology Applied to Infectious Diseases
- Introduction to R and RStudio
- Data Visualization in R with ggplot2
- Reporting and Technical Writing in R Markdown
- Epidemiological Data Cleaning
- Building a Simple Deterministic Model
- Introduction to Statistics and Probability
- Parameters

Key Results

Enrollment

In the 2024 implementation, a total of **2,208 participants enrolled from 27 countries, including 18 from Latin America and the Caribbean**. The participants represent a broad range of backgrounds in STEM and health sciences, with varying levels of expertise in data science, public health, infectious disease modeling, field epidemiology, laboratory research, teaching, and other related fields. Of the participants, **49% identify as women**, 35% as men, and 15% as other or prefer not to disclose. Furthermore, 47% of the participants hold a master's degree.

Completion Rates

Of the total 2,208 enrollees, **26% (577 participants) successfully completed and passed the course**, achieving a weighted average score of over 80% on the assessments. Additionally, 71% (1,575 participants) accessed the course at some point, and of this group, 37% successfully completed all course requirements. These completion rates exceed those typically reported in the literature for MOOC courses, which range between 7% and 10% ([Fu et al., 2021](#); [Gütl et al., 2014](#)) and rarely exceed 25% ([Jordan, 2015](#); [Duncan et al., 2022](#)).

Assessment Performance

For the participant evaluation process, an assessment was designed for each unit to be completed at the end of the respective module. To successfully complete the course and receive a certificate of participation, participants were required to achieve a weighted average score of 81% or higher across all assessments. The following section presents the results of all participants who completed the unit evaluations, where **the pass rate exceeded 75% across all units, and the failure rate remained below 25%**.

Engagement

In addition to the resources available on the edX platform as part of the MOOC, participants had access to a dedicated website. This website provided the R code for all course units, a comprehensive glossary, a Q&A section, and an error bank to assist with common issues encountered during the course. To further enhance engagement and support, we had a dedicated technical platform manager as well as a subject matter manager who could address questions related to the course topics and activities. Additionally, we maintained

an active email communication strategy, regularly sending reminder emails to participants and providing personalized guidance on completing outstanding activities to ensure successful course completion.

Finally, throughout the course, we had 15 open forums. The first was a welcome forum where participants introduced themselves, receiving a total of **848 contributions**. Additionally, there were 2 forums dedicated to addressing technical issues related to the platform and general course-related questions, with 253 contributions, including questions, comments, and requests for assistance. The remaining forums aimed to encourage participant engagement with responses to questions, challenges, or activities proposed in each unit. **These forums received a total of 3,526 comments.**

It is also important to highlight that these forums served as a valuable tool for fostering a sense of community. Participants actively engaged by commenting on each other's posts, discussing results, and even helping others who encountered errors or had questions about the code. This collaborative environment was key to enhancing the learning experience.

Satisfaction

For the 2024 implementation, evaluation, the following assessment measures were employed:

1. Satisfaction surveys for each individual unit.
2. A final satisfaction survey.
3. Pre-test and post-test, which include sections on 1) knowledge evaluation, 2) self-reported knowledge, and 3) self-reported learning intentions and motivation.
4. A forum for final comments and recommendations.

The course received an overall rating of 4.7, based on feedback from 478 participants. According to the unit surveys, **all units were rated 4.5 out of 5.0**. Among those who completed the course, 70% are from the healthcare sector, 27% from STEM fields, and 3% from other disciplines.

4,7 Avg. rating ★★★★★

According to the final survey, **80% of participants strongly agreed that the course effectively met its objectives**, while **85% strongly agreed that the course addressed the need for educational resources in Spanish** on the analysis and modeling of infectious diseases, was relevant to their professional development, and considered the context of Latin America and the Caribbean. Furthermore, **90% strongly agreed that the course facilitates access to quality education**, and **80% affirmed that it supports the promotion of gender equity**.

In the knowledge section of the pre-test, 1,129 participants completed the assessment, with 282 (25%) achieving a passing score. In contrast, 97% (568) of participants successfully passed the post-test, indicating a significant improvement in their performance.

Test	Total	Passed	Failed
Pre-test	1129	25%	75%
Post-test	586	97%	3%

In fact, participants who took the pretest achieved an average of 65.6% correct answers, indicating that, in general, they had a reasonable prior knowledge of the course topics. However, after completing the program, the average correct answers in the post-test significantly increased to 94.1%. This remarkable improvement suggests that the course not only reinforced the participants' existing knowledge but also filled gaps in their understanding.

In both the pre-test and post-test, in addition to assessing knowledge through specific questions, participants were asked to evaluate their self-perception of knowledge regarding the topics covered in the course. The pre-test revealed that participants had the lowest self-perceived knowledge in areas such as epidemic theory, simple deterministic models, working with R and tidyverse, cleaning epidemiological data, creating reports with R Markdown, and implementing simple deterministic SIR-type models using the R programming language. In contrast, post-test results demonstrated a substantial shift, with the majority of participants indicating significant improvements in their perceived knowledge and proficiency in these areas, as well as across the other topics addressed in the course.

Self-Perception of Current Knowledge

Reflections from Participants

"It's a great opportunity to find a course entirely in Spanish, which includes the history of epidemiology in the Americas. I love how educational the slides are and that the videos have subtitles. It's also great to have the opportunity to make a mistake once and correct it!"

"This course fills a gap in the available virtual, free-access offerings for using a tool like R with specific applications in health sciences. It addresses complex topics in a practical way... leaving you wanting more and eager to try it with your own data. "

“After several attempts, **I overcame my fear... or perhaps I overcame the fear of the unknown! With the examples and guidance presented in this course, it not only allowed me to dive into using R but also made me realize that it was simpler and different from what some had told me!** With real data—both from the exercises and my own—I realized how easy it is to manipulate and make them “speak” with R. What used to be a somewhat tedious task in Excel opened my mind to new scenarios... not only epidemiological ones, but also other things I work on daily.

Excellent course, and a thousand thanks! **The approach was clear, and the handling of the topics even more so!** Once on vacation, I will enjoy what I managed to download!”

“**This course has been one of the most comprehensive courses I have had the fortune of taking.** It contains a lot of information, and it is developed in a very didactic and applied manner. However, I believe **the time was tight because the practical units of the course require more time.** Overall, I am very happy and grateful to have been able to access this course for free and learn all these tools.”

“Thank you very much for all the combined efforts in this powerful initiative for those of us who are training and/or enhancing our knowledge on epidemiology. **It is a great commitment to ensuring the health sovereignty of countries.**”

“The course seemed very educational, interactive, and interesting in the way each topic was explained. **The “health detective” approach makes it more engaging.** I learned a lot about statistical concepts, the use of R markdown, and what I liked the most was the module on data cleaning and ggplot, which will be very useful in my work field. I am very grateful to the organization and hope they can develop more opportunities like this. Best regards!”

“I find that it has been a very complete and useful course. I liked that it was in Spanish and adapted to the Latin American area. **I work at PAHO conducting various trainings, and sometimes we lack material and examples to base ourselves on. I also liked that it includes an introduction to R, as it is an open program that anyone can use.** I really liked the modeling topics, and they were explained in a way that is easy to understand and follow. The only thing I found lacking was time to fully take advantage of it.”

Conclusions and Recommendations

Main Achievements

Significant Growth in Enrollment and Regional Reach:

- Compared to the 2023 pilot program with 223 participants, the course achieved a 890% increase in registrations, with 2,208 total enrollments.
- Expanded participation from 14 to 18 countries in the region, reaching new countries such as Bolivia, Costa Rica, Honduras, and Guatemala.

High Participant Engagement:

- Over **70% of enrolled participants actively engaged** in the course.
- Massive participation in the discussion forums, with **more than 2,500 comments and contributions**, fostering a vibrant community of learners and facilitating peer-to-peer knowledge exchange.

Improvements Based on Pilot Feedback:

- Adjustments made to the pilot course were well-received, enhancing the perception that the course reflects a broader regional perspective rather than a localized one.
- The creation of new resources, such as a **web page**, an **error bank**, a **Q&A section**, and **new video tutorials** for the R-related units, enabled more participants to achieve the learning objectives of these units.

Completion Rates Exceed Expectations:

- Of the 2,208 enrollees, **26% completed the course**, surpassing the expected rate of 10%.
- Of the active participants, **37% successfully completed all course requirements**, reflecting strong engagement and achievement rates among those who actively participated.

Exceptional Participant Feedback:

- The course received an **overall rating of 4.7 out of 5**, based on feedback from 478 participants.
- All units were rated **4.5 out of 5** in the unit-specific surveys

Areas of Improvement

- Expand the duration during which the course is accessible to allow participants more time to complete the content at their own pace.
- Consider dividing the curriculum into smaller, focused courses to ensure that participants can complete the content within 30 hours, addressing feedback that many spent more time than anticipated. For example, the curriculum could be split into two or three MOOCs—one focused on theory and another on practical applications with R—allowing learners to select courses based on their specific goals. This division would also better align with the free access time constraints of the platform, increasing the likelihood of course completion.